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12.00.10-МЕЖДУНАРОДНОЕ ПРАВО

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THE NATURE AND IMPORTANCE OF THE IMMUNITIES OF INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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ANNOTATION

This paper provides an extensive examination of the legal basis, extent, and problems of the immunities and privileges of international organizations and their personnel. The paper examines theoretical and practical determinants of immunity as a need for functioning, providing international organizations such as the United Nations and specialized agencies to operate independent of national jurisdictions. Drawing upon the principal international instruments, like the UN Charter, the 1946 Convention on the Privileges and Immunities of the United Nations, and the 1947 Convention on Specialized Agencies, the paper covers the forms of immunity granted to officials, representatives, and experts on mission. The author distinguishes functional from personal immunity, highlighting its legal functions and limitations. Analyzing real-life situations with the IMF, WHO, and ICJ, the article ponders over the delicate balance between these organizations' autonomy and the norms of accountability, transparency, and the rule of law. Lastly, the article stresses the need for a new perspective that safeguards the effective operation of international organizations along with their legal accountability according to standards of international law.

Keywords: international organizations, functional immunity, privileges and immunities, United Nations, accountability, international legal instruments, jurisdictional immunity, legal process immunity, The Charter of United Nations, The Convention on the Privileges and immunities of the Specialized Agencies (1947).

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XALQARO TASHKILOTLAR IMMUNITETLARINING MOHIYATI VA AHAMIYATI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada xalqaro tashkilotlar va ularning xodimlarining immunitetlari va imtiyozlarining huquqiy asoslari, ko'lami va muammolari o'rganiladi. Maqolada BMT va ixtisoslashgan idoralar kabi xalqaro tashkilotlarning milliy yurisdiksiyalardan mustaqil ishlashini ta'minlab, faoliyat ko'rsatish zarurati sifatida immunitetning nazariy va amaliy determinantlari ko'rib chiqiladi. Birlashgan Millatlar Tashkilotining Nizomi, Birlashgan Millatlar Tashkilotining Imtiyozlari va Immunitetlari to'g'risidagi 1946 yilgi Konventsiya va Ixtisoslashgan idoralar to'g'risidagi 1947 yilgi Konventsiya kabi asosiy xalqaro hujjatlarga asoslanib, hujjat rasmiy shaxslar, vakillar va missiya bo'yicha ekspertlarga beriladigan immunitet shakllarini qamrab oladi. Maqolada funksional immunitet shaxsiy immunitetdan ajratilib, qonuniy funktsiyalari va cheklovlarini ko'rsatib beradi. Maqolada XVJ, JSST va ICJ ishtirokidagi real hayotiy vaziyatlarni tahlil qilib, ushbu tashkilotlarning avtonomiyasi hamda hisobdorlik, oshkoralik va qonun ustuvorligi me'yorlari o'rtasidagi nozik muvozanat haqida fikr yuritiladi. Maqolada xalqaro tashkilotlarning samarali faoliyat yuritishi hamda ularning xalqaro huquq standartlariga muvofiq huquqiy javobgarligini ta'minlovchi yangi istiqbol zarurligi ta'kidlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: xalqaro tashkilotlar, funksional immunitet, imtiyozlar va immunitetlar, Birlashgan Millatlar Tashkiloti, javobgarlik, xalqaro huquqiy hujjatlar, huquqiy jarayondan immunitet, Birlashgan Millatlar Tashkiloti Nizomi, Ixtisoslashgan muassasalarning imtiyozlari va immunitetlari to'g'risidagi konventsiya (1947).

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**СУЩНОСТЬ И ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ИММУНИТЕТОВ МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫХ
ОРГАНИЗАЦИЙ**

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье рассматриваются правовые основы и проблемы иммунитетов и привилегий международных организаций. В статье рассматриваются теоретические и практические вопросы иммунитета как необходимого условия для функционирования международных организаций, как Организация Объединенных Наций и его специализированные учреждения, как возможность действовать независимо от национальной юрисдикции. Опираясь на основные международные документы, такие как Устав ООН, Конвенция о привилегиях и иммунитетах Объединенных Наций 1946 года и Конвенция о специализированных учреждениях 1947 года, в статье рассматриваются формы иммунитета, предоставляемые должностным лицам и представителям организаций во время выполнения миссий. Автор различает функциональный и личный иммунитет, выделяя их правовые функции и ограничения. Анализируя реальные ситуации, связанные с МВФ, ВОЗ и Международным Судом ООН, в статье рассматривается баланс между автономией этих организаций и нормами подотчетности, прозрачности и верховенства закона. В статье подчеркивается необходимость нового подхода, гарантирующего эффективное функционирование международных организаций, а также их юридическую ответственность в соответствии со стандартами международного права.

Ключевые слова: международные организации, функциональный иммунитет, привилегии и иммунитеты, Организация Объединенных Наций, подотчетность, международно-правовые документы, судебно-процессуальный иммунитет, Устав Организации Объединенных Наций, Конвенция о привилегиях и иммунитетах специализированных учреждений (1947 г.).

The concept of immunities of international organizations is an important aspect of international law. Historical notion of the word “organization”, designating an inter-governmental institution, was first used in the peace treaties after World War I [8]. International organizations and their officials are granted immunities to ensure that they can perform their functions without undue

interference from host states or other actors. Immunities can take different forms and are typically granted by international treaties or agreements.

To understand the privileges and immunities of international organizations and special missions also, it is important to provide an overview of the legal foundation for these immunities. While diplomatic, consular, foreign official, and head of state immunities are commonly known, there are other types of immunities as well. It is worth noting that international organizations and their officials are frequently granted immunities as a result of the constituent instrument that established the organization. The questions of immunity and inviolability are stated in a headquarters agreement of the organization with the member-states [1]. According to the given statement an initial question arises: `Why should international organizations and its representatives enjoy immunities at all? The second part of the research is dedicated to these questions. Firstly, we will discuss the concept and nature of the immunity of international organizations.

The immunities of international organizations are rooted in customary international law and are recognized by various international legal instruments. For example, the Vienna Convention on Diplomatic Relations of 1961 and the Vienna Convention on Consular Relations of 1963 provide for immunities for diplomatic and consular officials respectively. The Convention on the Privileges and Immunities of the United Nations of 1946 provides for the immunities of the United Nations and its officials.

As it was stated above immunity of the officials of international organizations is recognized in U.N. Charter. According to the Article 105 United Nations Organization enjoy in the territory of each of its Members such privileges and immunities as are necessary for the fulfillment of its purposes` [9]. Moreover, it is stated in Article that the representatives of United Nations members and officials enjoy such privileges and immunities as are necessary for the independent exercise of their functions in connection with the Organization [9].

It means that the organization enjoy immunities and privileges to exercise its functions in the territory of the States which are the members to Organization. In addition to this, the representatives and officials of the Organization are entitled to immunities and privileges in the territory of member-states as well as the Organization itself. Therefore, the immunity of international organizations and its officials is `functional`.

Functional immunity or *ratione materiae* [2] distinguishes from other types of immunities. First, functional immunity is granted to officials for taking any official act due to their functional responsibilities, regardless of their rank or position comparing to *ratione personae* [3]. Secondly, in comparison to *ratione temporis*, when the jurisdiction shows if the dispute exists, or it finds claim inadmissible functional immunity can spread on several periods of solving two or more disputes.

The next important document related to privileges and immunities is the General Convention, which provides for privileges and immunities for three categories of individuals who are essential to the work of the United Nations. These categories include: 1) representatives of member states; 2) United Nations officials; and 3) experts on mission for the United Nations. While representatives of member states are entitled to appropriate diplomatic privileges and immunities, United Nations officials, who are full-time employees, enjoy "functional" immunity. This type of immunity is defined in Section 18(a) of Article V as immunity from liability "for what is said or written by them and for all acts performed by them in their capacity as officers" [8].

The Statute of the League of Nations in 1919 first addressed the topic of immunity and privileges, but it only provided for "diplomatic" privileges and immunities for employees and the inviolability of the organization's property. However, these vague rules related to immunity of organizations required further clarification in order to become practical tools for international organizations officials and judges in national courts to determine the legal capacity of organizations to engage in a specific legal transaction or whether they are immune from legal action. Additionally, there was uncertainty regarding the extent to which officials of international organizations and representatives of member states to the United Nations should enjoy privileges and immunities.

International organizations and their officials are often entitled to immunities in accordance with the terms of the constituent treaties that created them [4]. International organizations and their

officials are frequently granted immunities in accordance with the provisions of the constituent treaties that establish them. In general, international organizations and their officials enjoy a range of immunities, including immunity from legal process, immunity from taxation, and immunity from seizure of property. However, the scope and extent of these immunities can be subject to debate and criticism, as they may be seen as limiting the accountability and transparency of international organizations and their officials [5].

1946 Convention expanded upon and helped implement in some states Article 105 of the U.N. Charter [9]. Article 105 provides that the representatives of U.N. members and U.N. officials shall “enjoy such privileges and immunities as are necessary for the independent exercise of their functions in connection” with the United Nations [4]. There is also the Convention on the Privileges and Immunities of the Specialized Agencies [10], which provides for immunities of organizations related to the United Nations under 57 and 63 of the U.N. Charter. As of July 2025, the Convention has 131 parties, including the Republic of Uzbekistan [20].

The aim of immunity for international organizations is solely functional, and it is related to the organization's specific tasks as outlined in the constituent treaty. The purpose of immunity is to ensure that the organization can carry out its functions effectively. This immunity is not a reflection of sovereignty, except in a very indirect sense, as it also serves to safeguard the interests of the member states of the respective organization [6].

The United Nations (UN) is an international organization that has immunity. The Convention on the Privileges and Immunities of the United Nations, adopted in 1946, grants the UN and its officials’ immunity from legal process. This immunity is intended to ensure that the UN can carry out its functions without interference from individual member states. The immunity of the UN is not absolute and can be waived in certain circumstances. However, the UN and its officials generally enjoy a high degree of immunity from legal action.

The United Nations (UN) enjoys full immunity from all legal process, as stipulated in section 2 of the 1946 Convention [8]. This is to prevent biased courts and eccentric litigants from interfering with the UN's functions. The UN's assets, archives, documents, and premises are inviolable, as outlined in sections 3 and 4 of the Convention. The UN is exempt from direct taxes and customs duties, while its staff members are exempt from income tax on their salaries (section 7 and 18 respectively). The Secretary-General and Assistant Secretaries-General are granted diplomatic immunity (section 19), while other staff members enjoy limited immunities, such as immunity from legal process for their official acts and exemption from military service (section 18). The Secretary-General can waive the immunity of a staff member if it would impede the course of justice, without prejudice to the interests of the UN (section 20). The UN is required to make provisions for appropriate modes of settlement of claims against it (section 29), and it has done so by insuring itself against tortious liability and entering into arbitration agreements [8].

The issue of how broadly the immunity of international organizations should reach has been a topic of debate and discussions. On the one hand, some argue that international organizations should be granted broad immunity in order to ensure their independence and effectiveness in carrying out their functions. This view is based on the principle of functional necessity, which holds that international organizations require immunity from legal process in order to carry out their functions effectively and efficiently. Proponents of this view argue that immunity is necessary to protect international organizations from politically motivated legal action, which could interfere with their work [5].

On the other hand, critics argue that broad immunity for international organizations can lead to a lack of accountability and transparency, and can undermine the rule of law. Critics argue that international organizations should be subject to the same legal standards as other actors in international law, and that they should be held accountable for their actions. This view is based on the principle of equality before the law, which holds that all actors in international law should be subject to the same legal standards [7].

International organizations should be subject to various legal standards, including those related to human rights, environmental protection, and international humanitarian law. Human rights

standards include the Universal Declaration of Human Rights [11] and the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights [12], as well as the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights [13]. Environmental protection standards include the Rio Declaration on Environment and Development [14] and the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change [15]. International humanitarian law includes the Geneva Conventions and their Additional Protocols [16].

In addition to these specific legal standards, international organizations should also be subject to general principles of international law, such as the principle of non-intervention in the internal affairs of other states, the principle of peaceful settlement of disputes, and the principle of good faith in the performance of international obligations. These legal standards and principles are intended to ensure that international organizations operate in a manner that is consistent with international law, and that they are accountable for their actions.

There have been several notable cases where international organizations (IOs) have enjoyed their immunity under international law. Here are a few examples:

The International Court of Justice (ICJ): In 2012, the ICJ ruled that it did not have jurisdiction to hear a case brought by Georgia against Russia concerning alleged human rights violations during a conflict in 2008. The ICJ held that Russia enjoyed immunity from jurisdiction under the UN Charter and other international legal instruments.

There are some examples of notable cases where international organizations (IOs) have enjoyed immunities and privileges:

The International Monetary Fund (IMF): In 2010, the IMF was sued by a former employee who claimed that she had been fired for raising concerns about corruption within the organization. The US District Court dismissed the case, finding that the IMF was immune from suit under the International Organizations Immunities Act [30].

The World Health Organization (WHO): In 2020, the WHO was criticized for its handling of the COVID-19 pandemic, with some governments calling for an investigation into the organization's response. However, the WHO enjoys broad immunities under international law, which limit the ability of affected parties to take legal action against the organization [27].

Some of the arguments against granting international organizations broad immunity include concerns about accountability, transparency, and the rule of law. Critics argue that granting broad immunity to international organizations can lead to a lack of accountability, as they are not subject to the same legal standards as other actors in international law. This can undermine the principles of transparency and the rule of law, as international organizations may not be held accountable for their actions. In summary, international laws aim to provide IOs necessary privileges while protecting autonomy. National laws are more stringent, impose conditions on immunities and expose IOs to national jurisdiction. International laws better preserve IO independence. (Cheng, 1953; Amerasinghe, 2005)

Overall, the scope, limitations, waivers, obligations and dispute settlement under national laws and international laws significantly impact IO immunities in different ways. International laws are more favorable for IO independence compared to potentially inconsistent and restrictive national laws. It is also worth noting that even if an IO voluntarily waives its immunity, it may still be eligible for certain procedural or substantive defenses in legal proceedings. For instance, an IO may be able to assert the defense of sovereign immunity or immunity *ratione materiae* under certain circumstances.

In conclusion, international organizations and their officials enjoy various immunities and privileges under international law, which are designed to protect them from interference by host states and other actors. These immunities and privileges include immunity from jurisdiction, inviolability of premises, and exemption from taxes and customs duties, among others. While these protections are important for ensuring the independence and effectiveness of IOs, they can also create legal and political obstacles to accountability and redress for alleged wrongdoing. As a result, there have been several notable cases where IOs and their officials have enjoyed immunity and privileges, as well as challenges to their immunity and privileges in cases of alleged human rights violations and other misconduct. Ultimately, the balance between immunity and accountability is a complex issue that

requires careful consideration of the interests of all stakeholders, including IOs, their officials, and the communities they serve.

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